

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF COMPUTER LEXIS IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The rapid development of information technologies in the 21st century has led to the emergence and global spread of computer terminology. English serves as the main source of these terms, while in the Karakalpak language many of them are adopted either directly from English or through Russian. This study investigates the linguistic features of computer lexis in English and Karakalpak languages, focusing on their structure, word-formation patterns, semantic characteristics, and adaptation processes.

Key words: computer lexis, English, Karakalpak, terminology, borrowing, calquing, abbreviation, standardization.

In the 21st century, information technologies have rapidly developed and penetrated into all spheres of human activity. During this process, computer terminology has become one of the most dynamic layers of the lexicon and has spread globally. English has served as the main source of these terms, and many of them have entered the Karakalpak language both directly from English and indirectly through Russian.

The object of the study is computer terms in English and Karakalpak, while the subject is their structure, word formation, lexical-semantic features, and the process of borrowing. The methods applied include descriptive, comparative, typological, component, and linguo-cultural analyses.

The analysis shows that computer terms can be grouped into several semantic fields: hardware (processor, disk, mouse), software (program, file, database), virtual entities (server, client, account), and process terms (download, update, encryption). Some borrowed terms demonstrate semantic expansion in Karakalpak: for example, account refers not only to “financial record” but also to a “social media profile”, while chat has developed the meaning of “online group communication”.

The formation of Karakalpak computer terms occurs through several mechanisms: transliteration (windows – vindovs, hacker – xaker), transcription (file – fayl), calquing (cloud computing – bulutli esapkitap), as well as creating neologisms from native words (baǵdarlama – software, mánzil – address). Abbreviations also play an important role (RAM, CPU).

The study reveals certain challenges in regulating computer terminology in Karakalpak: the existence of doublets (server – xizmatkor), borrowings through Russian (brandmauer, fayl), and the absence of a unified standardization system. Therefore, unification, the creation of a single terminological database, and the active use of national linguistic resources are essential.

From a practical perspective, the results of the research can be applied in education, the compilation of teaching materials, the development of electronic dictionaries, and the implementation of state language policies.

In conclusion, the comparative analysis of English and Karakalpak computer lexis reveals their interrelations, borrowing mechanisms, and the ways of employing native language

resources. This contributes to the development of Karakalpak terminology studies and enriches the language in the context of globalization.

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